

LEVEL SET OPTIMISATION FOR COMPOSITE FIBRE PATHS

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ABSTRACT

Advanced fibre placement (AFP) composite manufacturing technology offers a means to tailor the orientation of fibres for complex loading environments and significantly improve the overall structural efficiency. This paper optimises the continuously varying fibre angles using a level set method. The paths of the fibre tows are defined by constant level set function values, describing a series of continuous equally spaced fibre paths. Sensitivity analysis is used to update the level set function as part of a gradient based optimisation method to minimise structural compliance. The use of the level set function to define the fibre paths implicitly maintains continuous fibre paths during optimisation, producing a solution that can be manufactured using AFP. The optimisation method is demonstrated on two test problems, a cantilever beam and a plate with an out of plane load. These problems are solved from two different initial solutions to evaluate the dependency of the method on the initial solution. It is then applied to design an inter-tank plate of a space shuttle propellant tank structure.

1 INTRODUCTION

It is well known that anisotropic stiffness of a fibre-matrix composite is significantly higher in the fibre direction. Therefore the orientation of the fibres of composite laminates can be optimised to improve structural performance over the traditional quasi-isotropic fibre construction without increasing the weight [1]. Advanced fibre placement (AFP) manufacturing technology offers a greater flexibility in tailoring the structure of composite panels by laying down fibre tows in curved and continuously varying paths. This creates an opportunity for significant increases in structural performance and weight saving. AFP is an attractive manufacturing method for aerospace application where weight is critical, however designing the optimal fibre paths for a composite structure remains a challenge.

One approach is to optimise the fibre angles of piece-wise constant finite elements, however the continuity of fibre angles between elements is not easily enforced, often leading to solutions with step changes in fibre orientation between elements [2, 3], that cannot be manufactured using AFP techniques. It has been observed that the optimisation problem is also non-convex so this approach can be highly dependent on the initial solution [3, 4]. Material selection methods been used to select the optimal fibre orientation within an element and this approach has been seen to reduce dependency on the initial solutions, although only a finite number of fibre orientations can be used to prevent the number of design variables becoming excessive making it impractical to optimise for a continuously varying fibre angles [4, 5]. Lamination parameters can be used to optimise stiffness properties of an anisotropic element, making it a convex problem [6]. However the suitability of the solution for AFP manufacture depends on the construction of continuous fibre paths from the lamination parameters, [7]. Another approach is to represent the fibre paths as a curvilinear function, optimising their coefficients [1, 8]. This ensures the continuity of fibre angles in the final solution, but restricts the solutions to curvilinear paths only and may lead to a sub-optimal solution [3].

The level set method has fast become a popular approach to moving boundary and front tracking problems in a wide range of fields such as image processing, interface motion tracking, and topology optimisation, due to the flexibility in describing complex change of boundaries [9, 10]. The level set method uses an implicit signed distance function, known as the level set function, to describe the location of a boundary [9]. This paper outlines a new optimisation method for composite fibre paths using the level set method. This method directly optimises the fibre paths ensuring continuity of the fibre angles between elements like the curvilinear parameterization, but with a greater flexibility in fibre path definition using the level set function.

2 LEVEL SET METHOD FOR COMPOSITE FIBRE PATH OPTIMISATION

The objective function is to minimize the total compliance of a laminate constructed from a single layer of fibre composite under the applied loads,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Min: } E &= \sum_{i=1}^n \varepsilon_i^T C(\theta) \varepsilon_i \\ \text{Subject to: } &-\frac{\pi}{2} \leq \theta \leq \frac{\pi}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where E is the total compliance of the structure, C is the elasticity tensor that depends on the fibre angle θ , the strain tensor of element is ε and n is the total number of elements in the mesh.

2.1 Level set parameterization of fibre paths

The level set function is an implicit signed distance function, with values stored at the finite element nodes. The primary fibre path is defined by the locations where the level set function is equal to zero. The other fibre paths are defined by constant level set function values, describing a series of continuous equally spaced fibre paths through the laminate, shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Fibre paths defined by lines with constant integer level set function values.

For the purpose of mechanical modelling the fibre path is discretized to elemental fibre orientations on a finite element grid. Orthotropic bilinear shell elements are used, assuming constant fibre orientation within each element. The element fibre orientation is set to align with the orientation of the

constant level set function value path through the centre of the element. This is calculated as perpendicular to the slope of the level set function at the element centre, as shown in figure 2, using single point Gaussian integration and the formula in equation (2),

$$\theta_e = \frac{\pi}{2} + \arctan\left(\frac{d\varphi/dy}{d\varphi/dx}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial\varphi}{\partial x} = \sum_r \frac{\partial N_i}{\partial x} \varphi_i \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial\varphi}{\partial y} = \sum_r \frac{\partial N_i}{\partial y} \varphi_i$$

where φ is the nodal level set function values, N_i is the element shape function and x and y are the global Cartesian coordinates.

Figure 2: Definition of the fibre orientation within a finite element from the level set function.

2.2 Sensitivity Analysis

Equation (2) can be differentiated with respect to the level set function to calculate the sensitivity of the element fibre orientation to the level set function.

$$\frac{\partial\theta_e}{\partial\varphi_i} = \frac{\frac{\partial N_i}{\partial y} \left(\frac{\partial N_i}{\partial x} \varphi_i + P_i \right) - \frac{\partial N_i}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial N_i}{\partial y} \varphi_i + Q_i \right)}{\left(\frac{\partial N_i}{\partial x} \varphi_i + P_i \right)^2 \left[\left(\frac{\frac{\partial N_i}{\partial y} \varphi_i + Q_i}{\frac{\partial N_i}{\partial x} \varphi_i + P} \right)^2 + 1 \right]} \quad (3)$$

where $P_i = \sum_{\substack{p=1 \\ p \neq i}}^4 \frac{\partial N_i}{\partial x} \varphi_p$ and $Q_i = \sum_{\substack{q=1 \\ q \neq i}}^4 \frac{\partial N_i}{\partial y} \varphi_q$.

The sensitivity of compliance to a change in fibre orientation is calculated using the energy based sensitivity formulation of Luo and Gea (1998) [3], shown in equation (4).

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial\theta_e} = (-1 + 2\alpha - \alpha^2) \varepsilon_0^T \frac{\partial C}{\partial\theta_e} \varepsilon_0 + \alpha^2 \sigma_0^T \frac{\partial S}{\partial\theta_e} \sigma_0 + (2\alpha^2 - 2\alpha) \varepsilon_0^T \frac{\partial C}{\partial\theta_e} \sigma_0 \quad (4)$$

where ε_0 is the current strain vector, σ_0 is the current stress vector, α is the energy factor and S is the compliance matrix. The sensitivity of structural compliance to the level set function is calculated from equation (3) and (4) using the chain rule.

2.3 Optimisation procedure

The level set fibre path optimisation method to minimise structural compliance is outlined as follows:

1. Initialise the level set function values to describe the initial fibre paths of a laminate.
2. Calculate the element fibre orientation, θ_e , from the nodal level set function values.
3. From the element fibre orientations calculate the stiffness and solve for displacements hence stress and strain using a finite element method.
4. Calculate the sensitivity of the compliance to changes in the element fibre orientation using equation (4).
5. Calculate the sensitivity of the element, e , fibre orientation to change in the level set function value of node i , using equation (2).
6. Use the Hamilton Jacobi formulation and the sensitivities to update the local the level set function values around the primary fibre path using equation (5), where $\Delta\theta_{\max}$ is the move limit set for stability, ne is the number of elements that neighbour node i and are intercepted by the primary tow path.

$$\varphi_i^{iter+1} = \varphi_i^{iter} + \Delta\theta_{\max} \sum_{e=1}^{ne} \frac{\partial E}{\partial \theta_e} \frac{\partial \theta_e}{\partial \varphi_i} \quad (5)$$

7. Update the level set function values for the rest of the nodes using the fast marching method [10]. The level set function now describes a set of improved evenly spaced fibre paths.
8. Check for convergence, if change in structural compliance is less than user set critical value. If procedure has not converged return to step 2 to begin the next iteration.

3 NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION

The level set method for optimising composite fibres is demonstrated on two example problems. The material properties used are $E_L = 137.92\text{GPa}$, $E_T = 10.34\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{LT} = 0.29$, $\nu_{TL} = 0.021$, $G_{LT} = G_{LW} = 6.89\text{GPa}$ and $G_{TW} = 3.7\text{GPa}$. The level set fibre path optimisation method requires the initial location and shape of the primary fibre path to be defined. To investigate the initial solution dependence of the level set method each of these example problems are solved using two different initial solutions. The first initial solution is created from the solution of isotropic level set topology of the same problem, using material properties $E_L = 137.92\text{GPa}$ and $\nu = 0.29$. The second initial solution is created using arbitrary fibre paths based on engineering intuition. The initial primary fibre path is used to populate the parallel level set fibre paths in the design domain. In each example $\Delta\theta_{\max}$ is set at 5° .

3.1 Cantilever Beam

The first numerical example is a cantilevered beam of aspect ratio 2, with one side fully clamped and a transverse load applied at the centre on the other side as shown in figure 3. This is modeled using 40×20 bilinear quadrilateral elements. The fibre paths initialised by level set topology optimisation is shown in figure 4(a), the initial straight fibre solution consists of two horizontal primary fibre either side of the line of symmetry shown in figure (b).

Figure 3: Cantilever beam optimisation problem

Figure 4: Initial solutions to the level set composite fibre optimisation for the cantilever beam, the solid lines indicate the primary fibre path where the level set function, $\varphi = 0$. (a) obtained from level set topology optimisation with isotropic material; (b) Straight horizontal fibers.

The optimum solutions for these two runs are shown in figure 5 and table 1. Despite the significant difference in the initial fibre paths, both runs find similar solutions, shown in figure 5. Table 1 shows reductions in compliance from both initial solutions to the optimal solutions, of 14.27% and 41.50% for the topological optimum and horizontal fibre initial solutions, respectively. However the difference in angle of the arching fibre paths indicates that the two different solutions have been found in figure 5(a) and Figure 5(b). The difference in the compliance between the two solutions is 3.62%. This indicates that the level set method is dependent on the initial solution, however the qualities of the optimum solutions are similar. The level set solutions converge in 919 and 959 iterations for the topological optimum and straight fibre initialisations, respectively.

Figure 5: Solution to the level set fibre path optimization of the cantilever beam, the solid line indicates the primary fibre path where the level set function, $\varphi = 0$. (a) obtained from the topologically optimum initial solution, Figure 4(a); (b) obtained from horizontal fibre initial solution, Figure 4(b).

Table 1: Objective function value of the cantilever beam problem

	Initial Compliance	Solution Compliance	Percentage Difference in Compliance
Level set method with the topologically optimum initial solution Figure 4(a), 5(a)	22.55	19.33	-
Level set method with straight horizontal fiber initial solution Figure 4(b), 5(b)	34.24	20.03	3.70%

3.2 Out of Plane Loaded Plate

The second example is a square plate loaded out of plane in the centre and clamped at each of the corners, as shown in figure 6. The model was meshed using a 30×30 four-node bilinear Kirchoff elements. The fibre path initialised by level set topology optimisation is shown in figure 7(a), the initial straight fibre solution consists of four primary fibre paths, pointing towards the centre of the structure at $\pm 45^\circ$, shown in figure 7(a).

Figure 6: Out of plane loaded plate optimisation problem

Figure 7: Initial solution to the level set composite fibre optimisation for the out of plane loaded plate, the solid lines indicate the primary fibre path where the level set function, $\varphi = 0$. (a) obtained from topology optimisation with isotropic material; (b) straight fibers.

The solutions starting from both starting points are shown in figure 8 and table 2. Despite the visual similarities between the two solution fibre paths there is a difference in the compliance of the two solutions, the initially straight fibre path solution having a 10.5% higher compliance than the level set topology optimised initial solution.

Figure 8: Solution to the level set composite fibre optimisation of the out of plane loaded plate, the solid lines indicate the primary fibre path where the level set function, $\varphi = 0$. (a) obtained from the topologically optimum initial solution, Figure 7(a); (b) obtained from the straight fibre initial solution, Figure 7(b).

Table 2: Objective function value of the cantilever beam problem

	Initial Compliance	Solution Compliance	Percentage Difference in Compliance
Level set method with the topologically optimum initial solution Figure 4(a), 5(a),	3.72	1.51	-
Level set method with straight fiber initial solution Figure 4(b), 5(b)	1.81	1.67	10.50%

In both the above examples the level set fibre optimisation method was able refine the fibre paths to reduce the compliance of the structures, while maintaining clearly defined fibre parallel paths that could be manufactured using AFP.

4 SHUTTLE INTER TANK PLATE OPTIMISATION

An inter-tank plate from the external fuel tank of the shuttle orbiter launch system is optimised. The inter tank plate transfers the load from the solid rocket boosters to the fuel tank. A simplified model of the inter-tank plate is to be optimised, assuming a curved plate of uniform thickness with no holes. Symmetry is assumed so only half the plate is modelled. A 66×28 four-node bilinear Kirchoff element mesh is used to model the plate. The loading conditions and mesh are shown in figure 9. The composite material properties are the same as in section 3.

Figure 9: A: Shuttle inter-tank plate model mesh in 3D. B: Shuttle inter-tank plate model mesh and loading conditions represented in 2D.

Figure 10: Elemental fibre angle view of the optimum solutions for the shuttle intertank model, obtained by unconstrained elemental fibre angle optimisation. Shaded regions note the location of discontinuities in the fibre orientation that cannot be manufactured by fibre cutting, only one side is marked due to symmetry.

Figure 11: Initial solution of the shuttle inter tank model for level set fiber paths optimization with multiple level sets. The solid black and grey lines indicate indicates the primary fiber paths where the level set function, $\varphi = 0$.

The level set function is initialised manually by observation of an unconstrained elemental solution of figure 10, as shown in figure 11. Multiple primary level set paths are used in this model to satisfy the varying regional demands on the orientation of the fibre paths. Using fibre cutting and tow drop techniques, regions of different fibre paths can be constructed [1]. The translation of the elemental solution to a level set solution removed the discontinuous fibre orientation regions from the structure, however this increases the compliance of the structure by 14.42%. This demonstrates the challenge in translating an unmanufacturable fibre orientation structural solution into a design suitable for AFP manufacture.

Figure 12: Optimum fiber paths solution for shuttle inter tank. The black and grey dashed lines indicate the primary fiber paths where the level set function, $\varphi = 0$. Shaded regions note the location of discontinuities in the fiber paths, which can be manufactured by fiber cutting; only one side is marked due to symmetry.

The fibre paths are optimised using the level set optimisation procedure with the move limit, $\Delta\theta_{\max}$, set at 5°. The optimisation procedure converges after 440 iterations, producing the result shown in figure 12. An 8.28% reduction in the structural compliance from the initial level set solution, in figure 11, is achieved by the level set optimisation method's refinement of the fibre paths. The compliance of the optimal level set solution is 5.4% higher than the elemental solution of the same problem, as would be expected given the greater implicit constraint on the fibre angle continuity of the level set optimal solutions. However there are discontinuous regions of the elemental solution (marked by shaded regions in figure 10) that are not manufacturable. In contrast the discontinuous regions of the level set solution (marked by shaded regions in figure 12) would be considered manufacturable using fibre cutting. We further compare this solution to a quasi-isotropic solution, an eight-ply $[45, -45, 90, 0]_s$ composite lay-up with the same total thickness. The benefit here is significant with 93.0% decrease in the objective function for the level set solution, shown in Table 3. In this case the level set optimisation method has worked in series with the elemental method to find a superior solution with clearly defined and manufacturable fibre paths.

Table 3: Comparison of shuttle inter tank model results for element method, level set method and quasi-isotropic layup

Solution	Solution Compliance	Solution Compliance Relative to the Level Set Optimum solution
Elemental, Figure 10	0.0811	-5.40%
Initial Level Set, Figure 11	0.0928	9.23%
Optimal Level Set, Figure 12	0.0857	0.00%
Quasi-Isotropic	0.1556	93.00%

5 CONCLUSION

This has shown that the level set method was able to optimise the orientation of the fibre paths to significantly reduce the overall compliance of the structure and produce a solution that could be manufactured by the AFP technique. It is evident that the solution is dependent on the initial solution and the convergence can slow and these are areas of continuing development. However this work demonstrates the feasibility of using a level set method to optimise composite fibre paths.

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